

Psychological Safety	<p>Do the employees have to/need to work overtime, regardless of whether this is formally tracked in work time sheets or not?</p> <p>Are employee engagement surveys being conducted?</p> <p>*Are the practices, methods and indicators related to employee engagement and overtime aligned between teams?</p>
Effective Communication	<p>Does the organization provide an online communication tool/platform for intra unit communication and information exchange for its employees?</p> <p>Does the organization conduct context sharing/background sharing/alignment events for informing unit members' on each others' work?</p> <p>*Does the organization conduct context sharing/background sharing/alignment events for informing different units' members' on each others' work?</p>
Unit Autonomy and Empowerment	<p>Does the organization enable feature teams or similar organizational formations?</p> <p>Does the organization communicate the importance and potential impact of decentral decision making to its employees?</p>
Unit Collaboration	<p>Does the unit have a multi-stakeholder project setup among the unit members?</p> <p>Does the organization communicate the importance and potential impact of implementing interdisciplinary projects to its employees?</p> <p>*Does the organization have a multi-stakeholder project setup across different units?</p>
Personal Growth	<p>Does the organization provide an online learning platform of its own, or an organizational access to any of the existing online learning platforms for its</p> <p>Do the team members have any established learning targets?</p> <p>Do you support your employees to participate in employee trainings?</p>
<p><i>*Indicates a question that is asked for the product development scale</i></p>	

Design and Coding Practices	<p>Does the source code adhere to coding best practices? Are code reviews and static analysis systematically applied? Is the knowledge about design of the implementation sustainably preserved in the team? *Are the practices, methods and indicators related to coding aligned between teams? *Are the practices and indicators related to the design of a system aligned between the teams? *Is the overall architecture of the product systematically worked on?</p>
Testing	<p>Is the source code systematically tested with unit tests? Are integration tests automatically carried out in a systematic way? Are system and acceptance tests systematically developed and automatically executed? Are black-box test design techniques systematically applied? Are advanced unit testing techniques systematically applied? *Are the practices, methods and indicators related to unit, integration and system testing aligned between teams? *Are integration tests automatically carried out in a systematic way? *Are system and acceptance tests systematically developed and executed automatically?</p>
Data Driven Dev&Ops	<p>Do the services and apps collect feature usage data? Does the incident documentation serves as basis for development and operations decisions on feature level? Is there any established dashboard that allows real-time monitoring of development and operations data? *Is there any established dashboard that allows real-time monitoring of development and operations data?</p>
<p><i>*Indicates a question that is asked for the product development scale</i></p>	